

Metanoia: An Eco-Spirituality as the Need of the Hour

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This short article has been written in the event of the outcome of the dangerous and deadly corona virus epidemic that has paralysed the whole world. ¹The corona epidemic should not be seen as an isolated viral infection but it throws light to the destructive attitude of humankind towards mother earth. The crisis we face today is threefold, namely, the ecological predicament, the humanistic crisis and the theological dilemma. The one-sided anthropocentric worldview, which is controlled and carried by reason, made us forget the interconnectedness of reality. We fail to make a synthesis among the different spheres of life because of our lack of patience empowered by reason, and overconfidence that originates from the sensory knowledge. What is at stake then is a satisfactory and sufficient account of reality, an integrated understanding of the Divine, the world and human. We see this division in all areas of life, the body-soul split, the sacred secular bifurcation, the God-world-human separation, the past-present-future partition, science-faith severance, worship-work segregation etc. In this situation, we should go for a complete transformation, which removes the dichotomy and fragmentation and helps us view reality as an 'integrated whole' that accommodates human, the cosmic and the Divine. Humankind has to overcome the absolute

instrumentalization of the world, fragmentation of the human and the meaninglessness of the Divine.

In this world, nothing is isolated and everything is interconnected with everything else with the thread of non-dualism (*advaita*), i.e., from electromagnetic to divine and from human to angelic. We should not only overcome the dichotomies spawned by compartmentalisation, but also the estrangement of human person and nature and the dualism of the Divine and the world. The Divine, the human and the cosmos become less and less real because of the human blindness to see the unity in the mere apparent diversity. This fragmentation of seeing and knowing becomes the fragmentation of reality itself. For example, the myth of space and time: the myth of space with its threefold division of 'God above', 'human in between' and 'underworld below' needs to be re-interpreted. The myth of time with its stringent division of 'past, present, future' stands in need of new hermeneutics. We need to have a unified and integrated perception of reality. Underneath the diversity of common experience, there is a rhythm of harmonious oneness, which weaves together the inner vitality of life and reality. The beauty of this interrelatedness brings everything into a concordance.

Modern human person endowed with reason and assisted by a limited anthropocentric vision of reality has instrumentalized nature for his/her own egoistic purposes. Guided by the Goddess of reason and the objective thinking of science human being believes that the mastery over nature leads to the height of success. The adoration and admiration have gone after the progressive thinking of science. This exploitative mentality is considered as the progressive thinking of the modern world. Human person has looked down upon anything that has to do

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with the “mystery.” The mystery aspect of reality is perceived as something that is against the spirit of science. Human scientific and technological pride seems to be threatened and offended at the thought of anything beyond human control. “Mystery” has

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given way to “mastery.” Dazzled and overwhelmed by the astounding accomplishments of science modern human being thinks that the most efficacious approach to know reality is the experiment. However, through experiment we can never know the earth’s wisdom just as by experiment alone, we will never discover the mystery aspect of the human body and its real life. This experimenting attitude results in not only the disrespect of the Divine and the human, but also the exploitation of nature.

The estrangement of human person from nature is in fact, the real tragedy of the present day. Here, human person seems to be in dialectical opposition to nature. The civilized humans consider themselves as non-natural human beings. Their home is no longer the earth but the ideal world. They tame and subjugate nature. Nature is demythicized; there is no mystery about it. The sacred thread of collegiality that has woven the artistry of nature becomes broken and scattered into pieces. Humans have not only simply taken their sustenance from the mother earth, but also they have further exploited and violated her. The natural circle is broken if we convert *agriculture* which is a sort of love-making with the earth into *agribusiness*, which amounts to the violation of nature, significantly called world “resources,” for the profit of the exploiter. The “maximum” has replaced the “optimum.” The denuded forests, the polluted atmosphere and the stained seas are the best example of this exploitation.

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The earth is our mother. She is our very self. To destroy our relationship with nature is to destroy our very selves. In this sense, human survival is

inextricably linked with the survival of nature. The elevation of nature from objective level to a personal realm further implies the need of experience to understand her rather than to experiment. In this experiential level, we allow nature to penetrate us. Here, we are not only “seeing” but “hearing” too. That means, this process of experience is both active and passive at the same time. By allowing her to speak, we discover the earth’s wisdom. Human person shares in the life of the universe. In other words, human being as a microcosm is sharing the life of the earth, which is the macrocosm. The “real” cannot be disassociated from the bodily and it cannot exist without matter, though it does not consist of matter only. Life is not only about the material world. Life means the incorporation of the Divine in the human and its impregnation of all the structures of the material world. The world is no longer that which is fleeting but it is the very clothing of the permanent, the eternal and the immutable. This is precisely what we mean by *sacramentality* of the world. Many writers present human person as the prophet of creation, which is the complementary aspect of the priestly role. Since world is the symbol of God’s intentions and purposes it has to be read and interpreted correctly and act accordingly for the overall development of the world. Without this prophetic function, there will be no progress. As a prophet and interpreter, human person has to read the signs of the ‘time’ and interpret it for the future. This notion shows us to the dynamic attitude that humans ought to have towards the world, in accordance with the changing situations.

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Moreover, the role of a prophet is to point out the shortcomings, correct it, and in turn, reinstate the lost order and harmony and bring everything into a concord.

The idea that describes human being as prophet and interpreter of the meaning of God in accordance with the signs of the time catches our observation. How can humans discern that they have read and interpreted these signs correctly according to the creative purposes of God? Today, all claim that they have the “wisdom.” Some of them even claim that killing their fellow beings is in accordance with the divine purposes. Human being is

not satisfied with the present natural resources and s/he splits the soul of nature by splitting atoms (cosmic abortion) only to get more energy. This extra energy is used again against nature and fellow beings. How much natural energy (energy from oil, gas etc.) is made wasted for the sake of waging wars for the selfish motives of one or two powerful nations? It is commonly believed that many viruses are created as biological weapons in the laboratories of the big nations to use against enemies. Even corona virus, people believe, is also of such kind. These powerful nations are interpreting the divine meaning and purpose for others too! They themselves have acquired the prophetic role to bring everything into disharmony by destructive means such as wars, invasions etc! But, for whose achievement...their own! Are these advancements or disadvantages? Then, it will not be progress but an easy way to disaster and tragedy. The polluted atmosphere, the

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contaminated rivers, the extinct species, the exhausted natural resources stand as evidences to this ecological disaster. If this is, what is implied by creative and right interpretation of the signs of the times, then it will be self-destruction or suicide. We cannot draw boundary line for the cosmos or the human brotherhood. Is our nuptial bond with nature broken? Did the relationship with our beloved get divorced? These are the questions, which we have to ask ourselves in the light of the present crisis of corona epidemic. So, how can we differentiate the right interpretation from wrong ones? Here, we need a wisdom that helps us discern well so that we can transform ourselves through a radical conversion of mind, body and heart. Therefore, we have to foster an **eco- spirituality** that makes us to realize our wrong attitude towards nature and advocates a *metanoia*, - a radical *turning back*. A *metanoia* from *dvaitha(dualism)* to *advaita* (inclusivism), from self-elevation(greed) to self-expending (Trinitarian life-*perichoresis*), from life-negation(sin) to life-affirming (fraternity), from knowing the instrumental value of nature to knowing the intrinsic value of nature.

Conclusion

I conclude my article stating a notion from Daniel Quinn's book "*Ishmael*". In this book, a gorilla talks about humans (*takers* who exploit and conquer nature for their egoistic purposes), "You know how to split atoms; you know how to splice genes and how to send explorers to the moon. However, you don't know how humankind ought to live in harmony with nature" (not a direct quote). Let us learn how to live in harmony with nature. That is perhaps the need of the hour.

¹ I am indebted to R. Panikkar and A.R Peacocke (Cosmotheandric vision and the Panentheistic Vision respectively) to pen down these ideas.